

DISBOND GROWTH ASSESSMENT FOR BONDED JOINTS AND PATCH REPAIRS OF PRIMARY AIRFRAME STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

This paper develops a novel assessment approach of a generic patch repair specimen, namely the Double Overlap Tapered End Specimen (DOTES). The purpose is to analytically assess the applicability of a slow disbond growth approach for an adhesive joint under fatigue loading, and establish the required specimen parameters for experimental validation.

Stress-strain based adhesive failure criterion and Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) are used to investigate the stability of the disbond as it progresses. The results indicated that the slow growth approach would be feasible even when a disbond crack grows to a significant length.

Provided that a relationship between the fatigue crack growth rate and SERR value is determined through experiment, using the approaches described in this paper would enable a slow growth fatigue life prediction capability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Certification of bonded joints or patch repairs of aircraft primary structures requires demonstration of damage tolerance. Traditionally demonstration of damage no-growth under structural fatigue loading is required. In recent years, in order to reduce maintenance cost, a damage slow growth management strategy has been considered acceptable, provided the slow growth is predictable and without reducing the strength of the bonded structures below a required safety margin prior to scheduled inspection [1].

To help satisfy the certification requirement and implement the damaged slow growth management strategy, this paper presents a simulation model for understanding and computing the disbond growth behaviour of simulated bonded structures. This study mainly focuses on disbond tolerance assessment of metallic parent materials subjected to tension-tension fatigue loading. However, discussion about composite parent material applications will also be made where appropriate. This study is applicable to both adhesively bonded joints and patch repairs. In order to avoid repetitiveness, the discussion below will focus on bonded patch repairs.

Adhesively bonded joints have been widely used to repair cracks in aircraft structures. However, cost of the airworthiness certification is a significant concern for repairing damage in the highly loaded region [2]. Accordingly, Chalkley et al. [3] proposed an approach to minimise the costs of the certification process based on the generic patch repair design called the Double-Overlap Fatigue Specimen (DOFS) and the Skin Doubler Specimen (SDS).

According to Chalkley et al. [3], the DOFS represents the area over the crack in the parent structure where short disbond between the adherend and patch can be tolerated (the disbond-tolerant zone). The SDS represents the area at the outer end of the patch where disbonds cannot be tolerated (the safe-life zone) because the patch ends are generally tapered to minimise adhesive stresses and a greater driving force for disbond growth would occur in this region, as the disbond grows into a thicker region of the

patch. These specimens have successfully used in assessing disbond crack growth rates, optimum outer adherend end taper shape and other applications [4, 5].

In order to assess the whole process of disbond, a specimen including the full overlap region needs to be modelled. In this collaborative research project of ARC Training Centre for Automated Manufacture of Advanced Composites (AMAC), a novel assessment approach of a generic patch repair specimen has been considered. This specimen, called the Double Overlap Tapered End Specimen (DOTES), contains both “disbond tolerant zone” and “safe-life zone” in the bonded patch repair. Assessment of a long crack (from either end), up to the length corresponding to the ultimate failure of the specimens can be conducted. Hence, a more complete solution to predict the disbond growth and structure failure behaviour in bonded patch repairs can be achieved.

2 GEOMETRY OF THE DOUBLE OVERLAP TAPERED END SPECIMEN

An illustration of a bonded joint or patch repair is shown in Fig. 1. The middle line in the red section (Fig. 1) describes the position of the DOTES design in the actual bonded patch repair application. Details of the specimen configuration from the side view are depicted in Fig. 2.

Figure 1: Schematic of bonded patch repair representing the disbond tolerant and safe-life zone.

The geometry of the specimen shown in Fig.2 consists of three different parts, namely inner adherend (thickness T_i), adhesive layer (thickness 0.28 mm) and outer adherend (thickness T_o). A gap of 2 mm between the inner adherends is created to illustrate a crack in the parent structure. The thickness ratio between inner adherend and outer adherend is 2:1 while the selected value of T_o is 3 mm. The aspect ratio between the inner adherend and overlap length (L) is 1:30. Details of the boundary conditions for the DOFS, the SDS and the DOTES used in the modelling are illustrated in Fig. 3. The width of the specimen considered is 20 mm.

Figure 2: the Double Overlap Tapered End Specimen (DOTES).

Figure 3: Boundary conditions used in simulation a) the DOFS b) the SDS c) the DOTES.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS APPROACH

Finite element analysis methodology is developed using the commercial software MSC Marc to predict the initiation and propagation behaviour of the disbond in the bonded patch repair configuration. Due to twofold symmetry (red marked zone in Fig. 2), only a quarter of the specimen was modelled. This model also represents a single lap joint with full bending constraint.

In this study, the finite element model used is two-dimensional four-node linear plane-strain quadrilateral elements. The element size in the adhesive bond-line is set to 0.14 mm in most area. There are two elements through the adhesive bond-line thickness corresponding to the patch configuration (see Figs. 4 and 5).

Fine element size was considered in the adhesive bond line at the crack tip region. Accordingly, a patch mesh configuration (see Fig. 4a) was developed to reduce the computational cost. As the element size reduced, the 8 elements marked in red rectangular section of Fig. 4a are replaced by another patch configuration. Hence, the element size is reduced by half ratio as illustrated in Fig. 4b. The material properties used in this model are listed in Table 1.

Aluminum	FM 300-2K [6, 7]
$E = 71 \text{ GPa}$	$E = 2400 \text{ Mpa}$
$\nu = 0.33$	$G = 840 \text{ Mpa}$
	$\nu = 0.4$
	$\gamma_{max} = 0.19$
	$\tau_{max} = 54.4 \text{ Mpa}$
	$G_{IC} = 1.3 \text{ N/mm}$
	$G_{IIC} = 5 \text{ N/mm}$

Table 1: Material properties used for the finite element analysis.

Figure 4: Adhesive mesh refinement strategy a) Patch configuration b) Mesh refinement.

Figure 5: Implementation of meshing strategy a) disbond from inside b) disbond from outside.

3.1 Modelling Adhesive Material

An elastic-perfectly plastic material model was considered for the adhesive material (Fig.6). The linear response of FM300-2K material properties was defined through elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio (Table 1). In MSC Marc, the non-linear behaviour was determined through the equivalent von-Mises stress/strain relationship. The von-Mises yield criterion was used to determine the plastic response of the adhesive material properties. The following expression gives the equivalent von-Mises yield stress:

$$\sigma_{vm\ max} = \sqrt{3} \tau_{max} \quad (1)$$

Note also that in the FEM analysis, scientific shear strain (ε_{xy}) is used, which is half of engineering shear strain (γ_{xy}).

To ensure the material property was correctly implemented, single element analyses subjected to tension, compression and shear loadings were performed to examine the stress/strain relationship response. The shear stress/strain curve obtained from the simulation was compared with the defined shear stress/strain curve as depicted in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Elastic-perfectly plastic adhesive material.

3.2 Analyses Using Stress-Strain Based Adhesive Failure Criteria

The approach to predict adhesive joint strength based on adhesive strain energy density, developed by Hart-Smith [8] has been widely and successfully utilised. In the current study this approach is used via the FEM analysis.

The FEM analysis has a nature of mesh dependence, that is, lower strength of the joint would be predicted with a finer mesh at the stress concentration area. A characteristic distance method [9] is typically used to handle this issue. From previous analysis, an element length of 0.07 mm would be smaller than the characteristic distance for this adhesive bond joint [10], giving conservative strength prediction.

When predicting damage propagation with a stress-strain based failure criteria, an element erosion approach is commonly used. With this approach, mesh dependence would be less significant [11, 12]. This progressive failure prediction concept is considered in this analysis to predict the adhesive joint strength as function of disbond length. For a disbond crack with a predefined path, the erosion could be achieved by deleting the elements in front of the crack tip, or just separating them when the failure of these elements is predicted. Further explanation of this approach will be provided in Section 4.

3.3 Fracture Mechanics Approach

Two-dimensional plane strain analysis was selected to examine the strain energy release rate (SERR) along with considerations of joints geometry, loading conditions and the assumption of uniform crack propagation. The SERR components such as Mode I (G_I) and Mode II (G_{II}) were evaluated using the virtual crack close theory (VCCT) [13, 14]. The implementations were based on the nodal displacements and forces at the crack tip as described in Fig. 7 and stated in Eqs. (2), (3).

Mode I:

$$G_I = -\frac{1}{2\Delta a} F_y (\delta_{y2} - \delta_{y1}) \quad (2)$$

Mode II:

$$G_{II} = -\frac{1}{2\Delta a} F_x (\delta_{x2} - \delta_{x1}) \quad (3)$$

Total Strain Energy Release Rate (G_T):

$$G_T = G_I + G_{II} \quad (4)$$

Figure 7: Virtual Crack Closure Technique for four nodes element [15].

The SERR value was calculated through MSC Marc postprocessing VCCT results. The mesh-sensitivity of the results was examined. As expected, the total strain energy release rate tends to converge with a smaller element size (see Fig. 8). A logarithmic scale on the element size (x-axis Fig. 8) was used due to large scale of the element sizes. According to Rybicki and Kanninen [13], a good

estimation of SERR is obtained when the element size around the crack tip is small compared to the pre-defined crack length. In addition to the sensitivity analysis, the MSC Marc VCCT approach was also benchmarked against previously published results [13, 14] to be accurate.

Figure 8: h-convergence study for VCCT approach (Crack length = 0.28 mm.).

4 LOAD CARRYING CAPACITY ASSESSMENT

In this study, the disbond propagation threshold load was assessed through a series of static analyses with a pre-defined disbond length. Whether the disbond propagation under this load is stable or unstable is judged by if the calculated load is increased or decreased when the disbond length has an increment. Accordingly, the mesh was redefined as disbond length increases (see Fig. 9). The patch mesh configuration approach defined previously was implemented in this analysis to reduce the computational cost.

Figure 9: Illustration of fine mesh locations in static analyses a) 0 mm disbond length (initiation) b) 2 mm disbond length (only figures for the inside case are shown).

The results of the estimation are plotted in Figs.10 and 11. Fig.10 provides a comparison between the DOTES analysis and the DOFS analysis. The results are consistent between these two specimens. As described earlier the major difference between the two analyses is that in the DOTES analysis the disbond grows up to the total failure point (not plotted in the figure). A comparison between the DOTES analysis and the SDS analysis can be seen from Figs.10 and 11. The curves have the same trend but the load capacity of the DOTES is higher than that of SDS.

Fig. 11 shows only the result of the DOTES analysis. As can be seen in this figure, for the disbond initiated from the inside of the specimen (damage-tolerant zone), the residual strength would reduce as the disbond length increase from zero (initiation) to 6 mm; and then subsequently becomes steady. However, when disbond initiated from the outside (safe-life zone), the residual strength would reduce as disbond lengths increase up to 30 mm (where the outer adherend end taper terminates); and then become flat as disbond length further increases. In both cases the data shows a significant reduction of the residual strength as disbond length increases from the initial point on the curve (0 mm crack length).

Figure 10: Load carrying capacity of the DOFS, the SDS, and the DOTES. (For DOTES only results with disbond initiated from inside is plotted).

Figure 11: Load carrying capacity analysis of the DOTES.

In terms of assessment of progressive failure of the joint under a static load, the curves in Fig.11 suggest that the crack growth in both cases (disbond initiates from inside or from outside) is unstable. Particularly with a static load that is able to initiate the disbond or propagate a short disbond crack would rapidly rapture the joint.

When fatigue loading is considered, if the peak load of fatigue loading is below the residual strength curves, there will be no instant static failure. A fatigue failure would occur when the disbond

crack grows to the length with which the residual strength equals the fatigue peak stress. Depending on the ratio between the fatigue peak load and the residual strength, it is possible to have slow growth of the disbond under fatigue loading. The SERR assessment described in the following section could give a good indication about the growth rate.

5 STRAIN ENERGY RELEASE RATE ASSESSMENT

Similar with the above load carrying capacity analysis, the study of SERR was performed through a series of static analyses with a pre-defined disbond length and crack tip. Consequently, the mesh was reconstructed as disbond length increases. Note that the analysis results for crack initiated from inside indicate that SERR of Mode I is insignificant compared to the SERR of Mode II, and thus only SERR of Mode II is considered. A load of 10 kN was applied in all SERR calculations. Note that for a different loading, the curves of SERR against disbond length would have a similar trend as with these loadings.

The results plotted in Fig. 12 demonstrate the SERR conditions in the DOTES. For both the disbond cracks initiated from inside (Fig.12a) and outside (Fig.12b), the SERR initially increases as the disbond grows. They become nearly flat when the disbond lengths reach a few millimetres. They continue to be flat or increase slowly up to 120 mm disbond crack length. After that the SERR rises rapidly.

The SERR is considered as the dominate factor determining the fatigue crack growth rate. Thus, from the curves in Fig.12, stable crack propagation can be expected in a large range of disbond length. Thus, the results indeed suggest the slow growth approach would be possible even when a disbond crack is significantly long.

Figure 12: Strain Energy Release Rate a) Crack initiated from inside b) Crack initiated from outside.

6 PARAMETRIC STUDY OF ADHEREND THICKNESS EFFECT

As demonstrated by Hart-Smith [8], when the thickness ratio between the inner adherend and outer adherend is unbalanced ($T_i \neq 2T_o$), the adhesive bond loading capacity of the joint would be reduced. This could be used in the experiment to force failure to be in adhesive when this particular failure mechanism is of interest for experimental validation of an analytical model. The limitation of Hart-Smith's approach is that the SERR cannot be accurately estimated using a fracture mechanics approach. A FEM analysis is able to provide this important information.

A study on inner adherend thickness variation was conducted. Three variations were considered as specified in Table 2. The second variation (6 mm inner adherend thickness) was selected as the baseline of this parameter study. Fig. 13 plots the results, where only disbond initiated from inside of the specimen was considered. Note that Fig.13 showed that as the inner adherend thickness increases the loading capacity would reduce, whilst on the other hand, should an analysis be conducted where

the crack is initiated from outside, the results would show that as the inner adherend thickness decreases the loading capacity would reduce. Thus, adherend thickness selection could provide a control to the failure mode that could be useful in the experiment design.

Variation	Thickness ratio (Inner to Outer)	Inner adherend thickness (mm)	Outer adherend thickness (mm)	Overlap Length (mm)
1	1:1	3	3	180
2	2:1	6	3	180
3	3:1	9	3	180

Table 2: Parametric study of the DOTES design.

Figure 13: Effect of thickness ratio variations a) Load carrying capacity b) Total SERR.

7 DISCUSSION

7.1 Fatigue Life Prediction Approach

The following components would form a fatigue life prediction approach for the adhesive bond joint:

- To determine SERR value as function of disbond length (using the approach described in Section 5 above)
- To establish a relationship between the fatigue crack growth rate and SERR value through fatigue experiment (this experimental is essential and will be conducted as the next step of this research program)
- To determine the residual strength of the joint as function of disbond crack length (using the approach described in Section 4 above)
- Achieving the above first two bullet points would allow the disbond length to be estimated as a function of number of fatigue cycles through an integration calculation. Further with the above third bullet point the fatigue life can be determined, that is, when the disbond length reaches the critical value with which the residual strength equals fatigue peak load.

Note that the analysis described in Section 4 to calculate residual strength using stress-strain based adhesive failure criteria should be considered as preliminary. Mesh dependence could be further assessed and calibrated against experimental results. In addition, the residual strength prediction may alternatively be based on a fracture mechanics criterion (that is, the residual strength value as function

of disbond crack length is determined with the criterion that the SERR reaches the critical value). The effectiveness of these two approaches can be compared and assessed against experimental data.

7.2 Slow Growth Approach – Further Factors to Consider

Though the fatigue life of a bonded joint may possibly be predicted using the procedure described in Section 7.1 above, the applicability of slow growth management approach is further complicated by the factors of static strength safety margin requirement and defect tolerance requirement. The static strength safety margin requirement means the residual strength needs to be at least 1.5 times¹ of the fatigue peak load (otherwise a repair would be required). The defect tolerance requirement means an NDI detectable disbond size has to be assumed when the pristine specimen strength is estimated. For a practical application of a slow growth approach, these factors also need to be considered. Only within these constraints and if the fatigue loading is still able to propagate the disbond crack, could the slow growth approach be utilised.

Detailed discussion about how to further consider these factors would be lengthy and thus will not be provided in this short paper.

7.3 Further SERR Assessment

Significant more work could be further conducted in assessing SERR. Generically, for adhesive bonded joint analyses, a nominal SERR in the form of $G_I/G_{IC} + G_{II}/G_{IIC}$ should be considered. Since G_I and G_{II} can vary significantly depending on the specimen configurations, such as specimen symmetry, single crack or multi-cracks, bending constraint condition, patch end taper shape, etc., G_I and G_{II} effects need to be properly counted.

It should also be noted that the compressive loading behaviour could be dominant in the case of repairing for composite parent structures. Accordingly, Mode I failure could become critical for the disbond crack initiated from the outside of the specimen, since the through-thickness stress becomes positive peel stress that tends to open the disbond crack from that end.

As mentioned above the residual strength prediction may alternatively be based on a fracture mechanics criterion.

7.4 Joint Failure Mode

This study is focused on investigation of adhesive failure and thus the aim is design of the specimen to obtain fatigue growth of disbands without fatigue failure of the inner adherend. The approach described in Section 6 may be used to control the failure mode.

However, in a real repair application, a design to achieve the inner adherend failure outside the joint is most desirable. These two considerations should not be confused with each other. This study is just to provide an approach to accurately estimate adhesive failure behaviour, which would contribute to proper design of a desirable adhesive joint.

8 CONCLUSIVE REMARKS

A finite element analysis was conducted over the whole overlap length of an adhesive bonded double lap joint. The residual strength of the joint as a function of disbond length was determined using an adhesive element failure criterion. The strain energy release rate (SERR) was determined using virtual crack close technique (VCCT), which was used to assess the trend of disbond crack growth rate as a function of disbond length. Disbond cracks initiated both from inside and outside of the overlap region were analysed.

The analyses indicated that disbond would result in a significant reduction of the residual strength compared with the pristine state. The residual strength becomes nearly constant after 6 mm and 30 mm lengths respectively for disbond cracks initiated from inside and outside, before it drops after the disbond crack lengths increase to over 100 mm. In terms of assessment of progressive failure of the

¹ Residual strength needs to 1.5 times design limit load, or below this but above design limit load only for a short while which can be confidently picked up by scheduled inspection.

joint under a static load, these results suggest that the crack growth in both cases (disbond initiates from inside or from outside) is unstable. Particularly with a static load that is able to initiate the disbond or propagate a short disbond crack would rapidly rupture the joint. When a fatigue loading with the peak load below the residual strength curves is considered, there will be no instant static failure. A fatigue failure would occur when the disbond crack grows to the length with which the residual strength equals the fatigue peak stress.

The SERR results suggested that the crack growth rates would increase initially as the disbond crack grows. In the disbond length range from 5 to 120 mm the crack growth rates become flat or slowly increase as the crack length increases; beyond 120 mm, the crack growth rate would increase rapidly up to failure. Thus, the results indeed suggest the slow growth approach would be possible even when a disbond crack is significantly long.

A detailed description of fatigue life prediction procedure for the adhesive bond joint is given. With this, plus considerations for the factors of the static strength safety margin requirement and manufacture defect tolerance requirement, a slow disbond growth management approach would be feasible.

9 PLANNED FUTURE WORK

The simulation model proposed in this paper is the first step for the input toward the certification process. Significant further work is planned, including to validate this analytical model by testing strip coupon specimens, and then extend the research to assess large repair panel (Fig.1), computationally and experimentally.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. A. Administration, "Composite Aircraft Structure," vol. AC20-107B, 8 September 2009.
- [2] P. Chalkley and A. Baker, "Development of a generic repair joint for certification of bonded composite repairs," *International journal of adhesion and adhesives*, vol. 19, no. 2-3, pp. 121-132, 1999.
- [3] P. Chalkley, C. Wang, and A. Baker, "Fatigue testing of generic bonded joints," in *Advances in the bonded composite repair of metallic aircraft structure*: Elsevier, 2002, pp. 103-126.
- [4] P. Cheuk, L. Tong, A. Rider, and J. Wang, "Analysis of energy release rate for fatigue cracked metal-to-metal double-lap shear joints," *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 181-191, 2005.
- [5] J. Wang, A. Rider, M. Heller, and R. Kaye, "Theoretical and experimental research into optimal edge taper of bonded repair patches subject to fatigue loadings," *International journal of adhesion and adhesives*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 410-426, 2005.
- [6] N. Chowdhury, W. K. Chiu, J. Wang, and P. Chang, "Static and fatigue testing thin riveted, bonded and hybrid carbon fiber double lap joints used in aircraft structures," *Composite Structures*, vol. 121, pp. 315-323, 2015.
- [7] R. A. A. Force, "Composite materials and adhesive bonded repairs, engineering and design procedures " vol. (AAP 7021.016-1).
- [8] L. J. Hart-Smith, "Adhesive-Bonded Double Lap Joints," *NASA Langley Research Center Report NASA CR-112235*, 1973.
- [9] J. M. Whitney and R. Nuismer, "Stress fracture criteria for laminated composites containing stress concentrations," *Journal of composite materials*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 253-265, 1974.
- [10] A. Sheppard, D. Kelly, and L. Tong, "A damage zone model for the failure analysis of adhesively bonded joints," *International journal of adhesion and adhesives*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 385-400, 1998.

- [11] J. Wang, P. Callus, and M. Bannister, "Experimental and numerical investigation of the tension and compression strength of un-notched and notched quasi-isotropic laminates," *composite Structures*, vol. 64, no. 3-4, pp. 297-306, 2004.
- [12] J. Wang and R. Bartholomeusz, "Ballistic damage in carbon/epoxy composite panels," *Journal of Battlefield Technology*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 7, 2004.
- [13] E. F. Rybicki and M. F. Kanninen, "A finite element calculation of stress intensity factors by a modified crack closure integral," *Engineering fracture mechanics*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 931-938, 1977.
- [14] R. Krueger, "Virtual crack closure technique: history, approach, and applications," *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, vol. 57, no. 2, pp. 109-143, 2004.
- [15] M. Marc and A. Volume, "Theory and user information," *MSC Corp*, vol. 8, 2018.